

The Leadership Models in Education

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Abstract:- In this study the leadership models are reported. In education, as in any organization, the role of leadership is crucial. The knowledge of the leadership models is important because the model of the educational leadership affects the school effectiveness. These models have been developed through the various leadership theories that date from the late 19th century to the present day. Also, the present study, observes the concept of educational leadership and points out the differences in the concept of administration.

Keywords:- Management, Administration, Educational Leadership, Leadership Models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Management and administration, as a social phenomenon, have existed since the time man felt the need to cooperate with his fellow human beings to achieve common goals. Education is a fundamental social function and school is an educational organization whose purpose is to provide the good of education. In a society where social, cultural and economic conditions are constantly changing, the function of the school unit is affected. The school is an open organization that has a constant interaction with the local and the wider community. In such a context, the role of the leadership is a subject of study of particular interest. The results of the researches reinforce the view that leadership is a multidimensional concept that affects the variables that are connected with schools and students.

II. THE CONCEPT OF LEADERSHIP

Leadership is one of the central concepts in the theory of Management Science. Yukl (Katsaros, 2008: p. 96) argues that, "like all conceptual constructions in the social sciences, the definition of leadership is arbitrary and highly subjective. Some definitions are more useful than others, but there is no right definition".

A common place in most definitions is the view of leadership as a process of exerting influence. This means that leadership has an influence on the behavior of others (Katsaros, 2008). Thus, for Bush, 2008 (Mourikis, M., 2016) "leadership is the process of exerting influence. Influence is defined as the ability to influence the behavior of others. Influence is the dynamic informal two-way interactive indeterminate aspect of power that causes voluntary behavior compliance and is clearly distinguished from authority, which is the structural and formal aspect of power.

III. HOW LEADERSHIP DIFFERS FROM MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION

In the early years of research, the basic concepts associated with the organization and operation of educational organizations were Administration or Management. The concept of Leadership appeared as an alternative form of these two concepts, having a broader content (Balias E., Bestias, 2016: pp.166-168). The majority of researchers argue that management and administration are two concepts that may be complementary but have clearly distinct roles. According to Dimmock, Leithwood & Duke (Katsaros, 2008: p. 98) "the management concerns the implementation of the policy and the maintenance of the functionality and the efficiency of the organization at the level of its daily operations, while the leadership has the role of policy making, dealing with changes and generally sets high goals related to staff improvement".

Management therefore refers to a scientifically and rationally defined system of techniques, procedures, tools and rules as a basis for designing, planning, organizing, implementing and achieving organizational goals. On the other hand, leadership "refers to innovations which improve the way an organization operates, and change the behavior of individuals when conditions require it" (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 167).

Whatever the distinction between the two concepts is, great importance must be attached to both and they must complement one another. As Kotter, 1988 (Burandas, 2002: p. 313) notes, "management faces primarily the complexity of modern organizations while leadership faces the changes of the modern world". The leadership of education is complex since the school, as an organization, does not have a single purpose. Its purpose "differs depending on who it concerns, that is, there is a different purpose for teachers, students, student families, politicians, businessmen" (Mavrogiorgos, 2008: 128). Another element that makes the school leadership complex is "the lack of administrative autonomy that increases with the centralism and the large bureaucracy that prevails, as well as the lack of competition that does not lead it in a direction of rationalization and modernization" (Kotsikis, 2003: p. 47).

These are the peculiarities of education and therefore the transfer of management principles to the education should be avoided. On the contrary, "appropriate adaptation of these principles to the special conditions of education is required" (Andreou, 1999: p. 10). For Bolam (Balias E., Bestias, 2016: p. 168) management is defined as "the executive function for the implementation of agreed policy terms", while leadership has the responsibility for the elaboration of policy and organizational transformation when it is feasible". So

leadership is associated with change while management with a management activity. For Carnall (Balias E., Bestias, 2016: 169) leadership is the key to managing organizations in times of crisis and constant change, while all management actions are a combination of knowledge and skills applied in practice.

IV. THE CONCEPT OF EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP

The educational leadership deals with the operation of schools and educational organizations in general. An organization is "a system of consciously coordinated activities or forces exercised by two or more persons who communicate in order to achieve one or more specific common goals" (Katsaros, 2008: p. 17). The school is an organization and "is a decentralized public and private service, whose operation is limited by the relevant legislation, while its organization follows the hierarchical model and is based on the existence of rules and the formation of positions and roles with specific tasks" (Mavrogiorgos, 2008: p. 125).

Leadership is "the specialized human activity that develops in all types of educational organizations and seeks to achieve the purposes of education by utilizing the available resources, human and material, through functions such as organization, management, coordination and control" (Saitis, 2000: 24). For Saitis (2000) the organization includes a) the arrangement, b) the coordination, c) the settlement of the parts of a set of persons and things, d) the division of work. Another way of defining educational leadership is to describe it as "a process of coordinating people, students, teachers, supporting staff, activities and existing means to provide education in a more effective way" (Koutouzis, 1999: 35). For Kambouridis, 2002 the goal of the Educational Administration is the efficient and orderly operation of the educational unit through the realization of the following objectives (Kambouridis, 2002, p. 14):

- To unite human and material resources to achieve the goals of the organization
- To facilitate the adaptation of the organization to changes
- To maintain and improve human and material resources

Educational leadership can help education when there is the right school climate, the right leadership style, participatory leadership, empowerment of stakeholders and other factors. This emerged and was reinforced by the results of relevant research that showed that the functions and practices of the administration, contribute significantly to the creation of an effective school (Katsaros, I., 2008: p. 21).

V. LEADERSHIP MODELS

The interest in new leadership forms such as co-leadership with vision and empowerment began in the 1990s when researchers focused on leadership forms that reflected more "second-rate" changes, such as structural and culture diversification (Vassiliadou, D., 2014: p. 92). Over time we can distinguish four main approaches - theories of leadership, according to Burandas, 1992, Zavlanos, 1998 and Hadjipantelis, 1999 (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 169):

1. *The approach of the personal characteristics of the leader,*
2. *The approach of behavior,*
3. *The approach of the unexpected / contingent theories and*
4. *The new approaches / theories of leadership.*

A) According to *the approach of personal characteristics* "leaders are charismatic individuals, with innate, uniform characteristics, born and destined to lead". With this approach, factors and situations that could affect the effectiveness of the leader are set aside, such as the expectations of senior management, team members, the size of the organization, the organizational climate, and so on. (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 170). This theory has a significant effect on the understanding of leadership behavior and effectiveness. "Extroverted, conscientious and receptive people seem to tend to be more likely to show leadership behavior at least in terms of their personality traits" (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 305).

B) According to *behavioral theories*, types of leadership are flexible, leadership is not innate but is taught. The various forms of leadership behavior were categorized into two main components: human orientation and work orientation. Typical examples of behavioral theories are *McGregor's Theory X and Y* (1960). *Theory X*, is based on the principle that the average person does not like work, has few ambitions, seeks security, does not develop initiatives while theory Y argues that the average person loves work and develops initiatives. The leader who accepts Theory X is authoritarian, centralized, and accustomed to imposing sanctions on employees. In contrast, the leader who supports theory Y is more participatory (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 171).

Likert also dealt with *the approach of behavior* and developed the theory of *Four leadership systems* depending on the degree of trust the leader has in his team. These are:

1. The coercive-authoritarian (does not trust its subordinates),
2. The well-meaning-authoritarian system (trusts to some extent, shows that it is accessible but control remains in senior management),
3. The advisory system (subordinates are involved in some decisions but control remains in the top management) and
4. The participatory / democratic leadership system (full confidence, members are encouraged and involved in setting goals and making decisions).

According to Likert, the organizations that adopt the participatory system are the most efficient (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 172).

Within the framework of behavioral theories, in the 1960s was developed the theory of *Management Grid of Blake & Mouton* (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 172). This theory is based on two orientations: the leader-orientation to work and the leader-orientation to employees. These two orientations lead to five different forms of leadership (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: pp. 172-173):

1. The indifferent leader,
2. The service leader (low interest in team, great efforts to achieve goals),
3. The unstable leader (balanced interest in goals and team and uses rewards and sanctions),
4. The interpersonal leader (interest in team satisfaction but not in achieving organizational goals),
5. The team leader (high interest in both team and achieving goals)

The above two theories present an important disadvantage, which is the ignorance of the role of the external environment in the effective exercise of leadership. The answer for this is given by the advent of theories related to the characteristics of the situation (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 309).

C) according to *contingency theories - the approach of the unexpected*, the effective leader must understand and evaluate the dynamics of each situation he faces and adapt accordingly. Examples of this approach are the *Model of Tannenbaum & Schmidt* (1958) and the *Possible Theory of Fiedler* (1967) (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 174). According to *Tannenbaum & Schmidt's Model* there are 4 forms of leadership: authoritarian, persuasive, advisory and democratic. According to *Fiedler's contingency theory*, there are two leadership styles: 1) the leader's orientation towards the performance of tasks and 2) the orientation of the leader in interpersonal relations (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: pp. 174,175). Most of the research data supported the effectiveness of *Fiedler's leadership model*, in which the leader "is important to try to gain as comprehensive knowledge of the situation as possible" (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 313).

Another widespread approach in the field of theories that study leadership in relation to the characteristics of the situation is the *Course-Goal model* (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 316). In this model, too, the choice of the appropriate leadership style depends on these external factors. The leadership styles that a leader can follow are the following (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 317):

- Guiding (identifies to his subordinates what exactly is expected of them, guides and directs them)
- Supportive (develops good relationships with them and meets their needs)
- Participatory (allows increased participation in decision making)
- Oriented in achievement (his priority is to achieve high and difficult goals seeking to increase performance).

According to Northouse 2006 (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 318), "this model is the only approach in the field of leadership that constantly raises questions to motivate people, eg "How can I motivate them to feel that they can complete the project successfully, etc"

D) According to the *new approaches - perspectives for leadership*, the transactional or conciliatory and transformational leadership emerged (Papakonstantinou,

Anastasiou, 2013: 175) but also the charismatic leadership (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 321).

In these forms of leadership, leaders can manage in such a way that they go beyond the traditional boundaries of the manager of administrative and service affairs (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: 175).

The concept of *charismatic leadership* was first studied by sociologist Max Weber, who studied charisma as "a set of personality traits that set him apart from other ordinary people. People treat him as a gifted person with exceptional or even unprecedented abilities or powers" (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 321). According to the approach of Robbins & Judge, 2007 (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 321), there are four main characteristics of a charismatic leader:

1. Vision and communication
2. Personal risk
3. Sensitivity to the needs of people
4. Unconventional behavior (others perceive its way as original and sometimes unconventional)

A large number of studies have shown *charismatic leadership's* positive correlation with performance and job satisfaction as well as with ambitious work behavior (Vakola, M., Nikolaou, I., 2012: p. 322).

In *transformational leadership* the leader pushes employees to operate beyond expected levels of performance. Transformational leaders "have a vision, they communicate, they expand needs, they elevate employees' motivations, expectations, their values and goals, their confidence, and they cultivate their need for self-realization. Also, they encourage change behavior and create or modify conditions when needed, for the existence of an organizational culture that promotes collaboration, professional development and empowerment of employees, encouraging questioning and problem solving" (Papakonstantinou, Anastasiou, 2013: p. 17).

VI. CONCLUSION

The role of the manager is crucial for the effectiveness of school. It's very important for the manager to know the leadership models. Through his scientific training, knowledge of management science and its continuous improvement, he inspires, motivates, innovates and can effectively lead the educational unit so that teachers, students and parents can enjoy the positive effects of its efficacy.

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